

Challenges of human resource information system adoption: Evidence from two Ghanaian tertiary institutions

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Abstract

Human Resource Information System (HRIS) is one of the most important Management Information Systems (MIS) which contribute to human resource service delivery of an organization. This study therefore, seeks to identify challenges associated with the process. A closed-ended questionnaire was administered to 63 respondents from the University of Health and Allied Sciences (UHAS) as well as Ho Technical University (HTU) to identify these challenges. The study found lack of management support as the major challenge to the adoption of Human Resource Information System (HRIS). The study concludes that that lack of management support slows down the adoption of HRIS. It is therefore suggested that management should be involved and sensitized on the importance of HRIS to improve and enhance its adoption.

Keywords: Tertiary Institutions; Ho; Human Resource; Information System

1. Introduction

Management Information System (MIS) presents as a crucial contributor to human resource service delivery of an organization. Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) helps in the acquisition, storage, manipulation, analysis, retrieval, and distribution of information relating to human resources [1]. HRIS helps organizations by automating most of the human resource planning functions. The system has become an important strategic tool since it collects, manages and reports information for decision-making.

Despite a great effort by the management and the heavy investments that has been made on the information technology-based reforms at the various universities, implementation of HRIS still appears to be a serious challenge [1]. Even though studies have been done on HRIS [1] [2] [3], no such studies have investigated HRIS within the Ghana public educational sector. Specifically, no attention has been given to establish the factors contributing to the sluggish adoption of the system at the University of Health and Allied Sciences and the Ho Technical University. This study therefore, seeks to address this gap in knowledge by establishing perceived factors influencing the adoption of HRIS at the stated universities and challenges associated with the process.

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2. Methods

2.1. Study Design and Sampling Technique

An explanatory design was used to assess the knowledge about the determinants of HRIS from respondents from two tertiary institutions i.e., University of Health and Allied Sciences and the Ho Technical University, both in Ho using a closed-ended questionnaire. The population of this study is made up of staffs at the Human resource divisions and the Information, Communication and Technology division of each university. Information acquired from the HR directorate at HTU indicates a staff strength of at the HR department of 12 and the IT department has a staff strength of 17. With respect to UHAS, data available indicates an HR staff strength of 18 and ICT staff strength of 28 people. The study therefore has a total population size of 75 employees from the HR and ICT department of both universities.

2.2. Data Collection Procedure

The data was collected through the use of a self-administered questionnaire manually by the researchers to ensure a high response rate. The data was collected over a period of three months between August and September, 2019. Data collected from the questionnaires was standardized such that each respondent got the same question. Returned questionnaires were edited to correct probable errors and to sort out misconceptions and misunderstandings to ensure credibility of the research. In order to collect and organize data in such a manner that was acceptable and later used to conduct the required analysis. A total of 63 respondents filled and returned their questionnaires, representing an 84% response rate.

2.3. Data Processing and Analysis

Data obtained was compiled and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0. Descriptive statistics such as percentages and frequencies were used to analyse socio-demographic characteristics. Linear regression, means and standard deviations were used to analyse various data were necessary. P-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Descriptive Results for Socio-Demographic Characteristics

Table 1 shows various socio-demographic characteristics of respondents. Majority of the respondents were males 46(73%), in the age range of 31-40 years 45(71%) and had first degree as their highest educational attainment 39(62%).

Also, a good number of the respondents were junior staff 31(49%), had worked for 5-9 years 46(73%) and work in the human resource department of their institution.

Table 1 Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Background characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	46	73
Female	17	27
Total	63	100
Age (in years)		
21-30	12	19
31-40	45	71
41-50	5	8
51-60	1	2
Academic qualification		
Postgraduate Degree	14	22
First Degree	39	62

HND	2	3
Professional Certificates	8	13
Level of Staff		
Junior Staff	31	49
Senior Staff	20	32
Senior Member	12	19
Years of work		
1 to 4 years	15	24
5 to 9 years	46	73
10 and above	2	3
Department		
Human Resource	37	59
IT	26	41

Source: Field survey (2019)

3.2. Challenges associated with HRIS adoption

The perception of the respondents was sought to identify challenges associated with HRIS adoption. Table 2, indicates the response from respondents as to the challenges they associate with HRIS adoption. They showed their concerns with respect to various statements concerning the challenges they face. The results are discussed using mean and their standard deviation. Bakker [4] have established that overall mean values within the range of 1.00-2.32 indicates a low level of acceptance and an overall mean value between 2.33-3.66 signifies a moderate level of acceptance while overall mean values between 3.67-5.00 indicates a high level of acceptance. The findings were descriptively summarised with mean scores as well as the respective standard deviation scores. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Challenges of HRIS Adoption at UHAS and HTU

Statement	Mean	Std. Dev
Lack of management support acts as a barrier to the adoption of HRIS	4.613	0.49
HRIS is costly to implement and sustain	4.597	0.59
Low level of importance credited to HR functions in general	4.387	0.73
Lack of reliable vendor frustrate adoption of HRIS	4.317	1.02
IT firms lack the technical expertise to adopt HRIS	3.645	1.43
HRIS adoption face resistance from employees	3.307	1.48

Source: Field survey (2019)

Table 2 indicates that respondents strongly agreed or agree that lack of management support acts as a barrier to the adoption of HRIS (M=4.613, SD= 0.49). This agrees with that of Ang, Davies and Finlay, [5] who posited that there is always a challenge when management are to show their support to HRIS Adoption. It was also revealed that majority of the respondents strongly agree or agree that HRIS is costly to implement and sustain in an organisation (M=4.597, SD=0.059). The findings are in agreement with Heeks, [6] who postulated that HRIS is costly to implement and mostly there are funds at the department to support it.

Again, it was interesting to identify that respondents agreed that Low level of importance credited to HR functions in general (M=4.317, SD=1.02). The findings are supported Budhwar and Bhatnagar [7] who stated that HR has traditionally operated in “reactive mode” in the corporate sector, which means that the HR functions are brought into the picture only when there is a need. Furthermore, it was found that respondents also agreed that Lack of reliable vendor frustrate adoption of HRIS (M=4.317, SD=1.02). This is in line with the findings of Huang and Palvia, [8] who posited that when there is no reliable vendor of HRIS, adoption of HIRS is affected negatively.

Last but not the least, it was found that respondents agreed that when IT firms lack the technical expertise to adopt HRIS it becomes a challenge of HRIS Adoption (M= 3.645, SD=1.43). It shows that the respondents hovers around agreed

and neutral. This is supported by Teo, Lim, and Fedric [9], an organization's IT experience over time in the HR department has been found to have a strong effect on the overall success of HRIS adoption in an organization. Finally, it was found that respondents also agreed that HRIS adoption face resistance from employees ($M=3.307$, $SD=1.48$). This is the least of all the challenges questions that were asked during the data collection period. This is concredited by Bader [10] who also posited resistance to change affect HRIS Adoption.

4. Conclusion

The study concludes that lack of management support slows down the adoption of HRIS.

Recommendations

It is therefore suggested that management should be involved and sensitized on the importance of HRIS to improve and enhance its adoption.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that no conflict of interest exist.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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